

A GRAPHICAL OVERVIEW OF SOME ALGEBRAIC STRUCTURES AND THEIR ASSOCIATED APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Taking into account the most recent improvements in graph theory and algebra we can associate graphs of some mathematical structures to certifiable widely known applications. The aim of this paper is to develop the relationship through edge labeling among Latin squares of Moufang loops, constructed by additive abelian and multiplicative groups, its substructures and complete bipartite graphs..

Keywords: Moufang loop; complete bipartite graph; edge labeling

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• Introduction

Inspirable non-associative generalization, Moufang loop, of the group was introduced by the German geometer Ruth Moufang in [2]. The Minimum cardinality of unique non associative Moufang Loop is 12, proved almost 50 years ago by Cjein and Pflugfelder [6]. Chein gave new direction to construct $M_{2n}(G, 2)$, an infinite class of Moufang Loop, where commutative of the group G implies associativity of Moufang loop [4]. E.G Goodair introduced same innovative class of Moufang loop [15]. Modular arithmetic, the cycle construction are discussed in [10] to obtain the class of non associative moufang loops. Author proved in [2] that the associative part, nucleus of the Moufang loop is its normal subgroups. Article [14] written by G. Glauberman in 1968, materialized two important things, odd order moufang loop is

solvable and there are some Moufang loops with their trivial nucleus, while $M_{12}(S_3, 2)$ is solvable with trivial nucleus. If the order of finite Moufang loop is coprime to 6 then this loop has nontrivial nucleus, enlightened by Stephen M. Gagola III in [12]. Moufang loops are unquestionably the most contemplated loops. Non-associative Moufang loops can be observed in the forms of invertible split-octonions, unit norm split octonions and projective geometry (Moufang polygons, Moufang planes) see [7, 26, 27]. Mathematicians have discovered attractively all the non-associative Moufang loops of order less than 64 but for order 64 there are 4262 non-isomorphic non-associative Moufang loops [5, 15]. Kunen proved in [20] a Quasigroup with Moufang identity forms a Moufang loop and it is also notable that there is a unique two-sided inverse of each element in the Moufang loop.

In the ongoing time analysts are utilizing PCs quickly for the most part utilized applications and the subsequent methodology is graph theory. We can comprehend numerous certifiable applications by relating with a few graphs. Graph theory, came into existence due to the Königsberg bridge's problem in 1735, is the widely utilized bough of mathematics. Simon Antoine Jean L'Huilier, Swiss mathematician, and Augustin-Louis Cauchy, French mathematician, commenced to write some well known results of topology tremendously to encourage Leonhard Euler's work. In theoretical chemistry, the first name to associate chemical composition with trees was Arthur Cayley, British mathematician. James Joseph Sylvester, English mathematician, introduced the term "graph" and a sound book was written by Frank Harary, American mathematician, to attach social scientists, computer experts, engineers, chemists, biologists, mathematicians, physicists, geographers and astronomers. In an ecosystem, niche overlap graph can be used to discuss the competition between species see Figure 1.

Figure 1. A Niche Overlap Graph.

Within a network, signal transduction, evolutionary relationship, gene expression, bioentities, metabolic pathways, gene regulation etc. can be taken as vertices and their relationship as edges of the bipartite graphs. These graphs are very helpful to know expediently about RNA-seq and Microarrays [29, 30], yeast two-hybrid [11], protein-protein interactions for particular organisms, chemical reaction networks [9, 19, 21, 23, 28, 25], personnel assignment problem, query log analysis, advance coding theory, optimal assignment problem, projective geometry and document/word problem. Graph theory has become a significant, companionable and prolific tool to examine in various fields extraordinarily like software

engineering and chemistry. In the cutting edge world, it appears to be difficult to talk about properties of classical random graphs related with the models of certifiable complex networks. Rather than classical random graphs bipartite graphs can be utilized to defeat this trouble [16]

In the presence of M_{loop} , a non-empty set, and $\sim$, a binary operation, the ordered pair $(M_{loop}, \sim)$ is known as a groupoid such that $\forall m_1, m_2 \in M_{loop}$, we have $m_1 \sim m_2 \in M_{loop}$ and uniqueness of the solutions of equations $n_1 \sim m_1 = n_2$ and $m_2 \sim n_1 = n_2 \forall n_1, n_2 \in M_{loop}$ leads us to say this pair is a Quasigroup. We can take the Quasigroup $(M_{loop}, \sim)$ as a loop if there exists a unique identity element $e_{loop} \in M_{loop}$ such that $e_{loop} \sim m = m \sim e_{loop} = m \forall m \in M_{loop}$. We say a loop M_{loop} is a Moufang loop if any one of the following Moufang identities holds

$$(1) ((m_1 m_2) m_1) m_3 = m_1 (m_2 (m_1 m_3))$$

$$(2) m_1 (m_2 (m_3 m_2)) = ((m_1 m_2) m_3) m_2$$

$$(3) (m_1 m_2) (m_3 m_1) = (m_1 (m_2 m_3)) m_1$$

$$(4) (m_1 m_2) (m_3 m_1) = (m_1 (m_2 m_3))$$

$\forall m_1, m_2$ and $m_3 \in M_{loop}$. Associative parts $Nuc_{left}^{mloop} = \{m_1 \in M_{loop}; m_1 \sim (m_2 \sim m_3) = (m_1 \sim m_2) \sim m_3 \forall m_2, m_3 \in M_{loop}\}$, $Nuc_{middle}^{mloop} = \{m_1 \in M_{loop}; m_2 \sim (m_1 \sim m_3) = (m_2 \sim m_1) \sim m_3 \forall m_2, m_3 \in M_{loop}\}$ and $Nuc_{right}^{mloop} = \{m_1 \in M_{loop}; (m_2 \sim m_3) \sim m_1 = m_2 \sim (m_3 \sim m_1) \forall m_2, m_3 \in M_{loop}\}$ are said to be left, middle and right nucleus, respectively. The set $Nuc^{mloop} = Nuc_{left}^{mloop} \cap Nuc_{middle}^{mloop} \cap Nuc_{right}^{mloop}$ is known as nucleus of M_{loop} .

These three nuclei are coincident in case of Moufang loop i.e. $Nuc_{mloop} = Nuc_{left}^{mloop} = Nuc_{middle}^{mloop} = Nuc_{right}^{mloop}$. A non-empty subset N_{loop} of M_{loop} is known as a subloop of M_{loop} under the induced binary operation if N_{loop} itself is a loop and a subloop N_{loop} is normal in M_{loop} if $\forall m_1, m_2 \in M_{loop}$, we have $m_1 N_{loop} = N_{loop} m_1$, $m_1 (m_2 N_{loop}) = (m_1 m_2) N_{loop}$ and $(m_1 N_{loop}) m_2 = m_1 (N_{loop} m_2)$. An element $[m_1, m_2, m_3]$ of the loop M_{loop} is said to be associator and defined by $(m_1 m_2) m_3 = (m_1 (m_2 m_3)) [m_1, m_2, m_3]$, $\forall m_1, m_2, m_3 \in M_{loop}$ and the set $A(M_{loop})$, generated by all associators $[m_1, m_2, m_3]$, is the associator subloop of M_{loop} . We say a finite graph $\Xi = (\Lambda, \Sigma)$ is the combination of two non-empty sets Λ , finite set of vertices, and Σ , finite set of edges. If Ξ does not contain multiple edges and loops then it is a simple graph. Complete graph is the type of simple graph in which there is an edge between any two distinct vertices. Let $|\Lambda_1| = m$ and $|\Lambda_2| = n$ are the cardinalities of two non-empty subsets of Λ , a simple graph $\Xi = (\Lambda, \Sigma)$ is called 2-mode network, bigraph or bipartite graph, denoted by $K_{m,n}$, such that for each edge $e = (\varphi, \psi) \in \Sigma$ we have $\varphi \in \Lambda_1, \psi \in \Lambda_2$ with $\Lambda = \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2$ and $\emptyset = \Lambda_1 \cap \Lambda_2$ [24, 17]. In case of $|\Lambda_1| = |\Lambda_2|$ this graph is known as balanced bipartite graph. In simple words, we can say Edge labeling is a process to assign a number or symbol to an edge in the graph i.e. mathematically, edge labeling is just a mapping $\chi : \Sigma \rightarrow \Delta$, set of symbols, and Ξ is known as edge-labeled graph with this χ [8, 13, 18, 1, 22, 3, 31]. Through edge labeling, we are able to relate Moufang Latin square to complete bipartite graph without paying attention on algebraic operation. In the Figure 2, element $(\beta, 1)$ shows an edge corresponding to two arbitrary vertices M and N. Therefore $K_{4,4}$ is the associated graph of

Figure 2. Edge $(\beta, 1)$

$(\alpha, 0)$	$(\alpha, 1)$	$(\beta, 0)$	$(\beta, 1)$
$(\alpha, 1)$	$(\alpha, 0)$	$(\beta, 1)$	$(\beta, 0)$
$(\beta, 0)$	$(\beta, 1)$	$(\alpha, 1)$	$(\alpha, 0)$
$(\beta, 1)$	$(\beta, 0)$	$(\alpha, 0)$	$(\alpha, 1)$

Table 1. Latin Square Of Order 4

- **Materials and Methods**

A mapping $\xi : \Theta_1 \times \Theta_1 \rightarrow \Theta_2$ defined by;

$$\xi(1\Theta_1, \%) = \xi(\%, 1\Theta_1) = 0\Theta_2, \forall \% \in \Theta_1,$$

is called a factor set, where Θ_1 and Θ_2 be the multiplicative and additive abelian groups respectively. This factor set can help us to introduce $\sim$, a binary operation, on $\Theta_1 \times \Theta_2$ as follows;

$$(\%_1, \eta_1) \sim (\%_2, \eta_2) = (\%_1\%_2, \eta_1 + \eta_2 + \xi(\%_1, \%_2)) \quad \forall \%_1, \%_2 \in \Theta_1 \text{ and } \forall \eta_1, \eta_2 \in \Theta_2.$$

Obviously this algebraic structure with the neutral element, $\text{eloop} = (1\Theta_1, 0\Theta_2)$, and inverse element, $(\%, \eta)^{-1} = (\%^{-1}, -\eta - \xi(\%, \%^{-1}))$ of $(\%, \eta)$, is a loop denoted by $M_{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi)$. Our next notion is to create an identity in the form of this ξ

Theorem 2.1. By the previous notations, $M_{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi)$ is a Moufang loop if and only if

$$(5) \quad \xi(\%_1, \%_2) + \xi(\%_3, \%_1) - \xi(\%_2, \%_3) = \xi(\%_1, \%_2\%_3) + \xi(\%_1 \cdot \%_2\%_3, \%_1) - \xi(\%_1\%_2, \%_3\%_1)$$

$$\forall \%_1, \%_2, \%_3 \in \Theta_1.$$

Proof. Let $M_{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi)$ is a Moufang loop then $\forall (\%_1, \eta_1), (\%_2, \eta_2), (\%_3, \eta_3) \in M_{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi)$

$$\begin{aligned} & [(\%_1, \eta_1) \sim (\%_2, \eta_2)] \sim [(\%_3, \eta_3) \sim (\%_1, \eta_1)] \\ &= [(\%_1\%_2, \eta_1 + \eta_2 + \xi(\%_1, \%_2))] \sim [(\%_3\%_1, \eta_3 + \eta_1 + \xi(\%_3, \%_1))] \\ &= ((\%_1\%_2)(\%_3\%_1), \eta_1 + \eta_2 + \eta_3 + \eta_1 + \xi(\%_1, \%_2) + \xi(\%_3, \%_1) + \xi(\%_1\%_2, \%_3\%_1)) \\ &= ((\%_1\%_2)(\%_3\%_1), 2\eta_1 + \eta_2 + \eta_3 + \xi(\%_1, \%_2) + \xi(\%_3, \%_1) + \xi(\%_1\%_2, \%_3\%_1)) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & [(\%_1, \eta_1) \sim \{(\%_2, \eta_2) \sim (\%_3, \eta_3)\}] \sim (\%_1, \eta_1) \\ &= [(\%_1, \eta_1) \sim (\%_2\%_3, \eta_2 + \eta_3 + \xi(\%_2, \%_3))] \sim (\%_1, \eta_1) \\ &= (\%_1 \cdot \%_2\%_3, \eta_1 + \eta_2 + \eta_3 + \xi(\%_2, \%_3) + \xi(\%_1, \%_2\%_3)) \sim (\%_1, \eta_1) \\ &= (\%_1(\%_2\%_3) \cdot \%_1, 2\eta_1 + \eta_2 + \eta_3 + \xi(\%_2, \%_3) + \xi(\%_1, \%_2\%_3) + \xi(\%_1 \cdot \%_2\%_3, \%_1)). \end{aligned}$$

Since $M_{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi)$ is a Moufang loop so , we have

$$\xi(\%_1, \%_2) + \xi(\%_3, \%_1) - \xi(\%_2, \%_3) = \xi(\%_1, \%_2\%_3) + \xi(\%_1 \cdot \%_2\%_3, \%_1) - \xi(\%_1\%_2, \%_3\%_1).$$

It completes the proof

2.1. Moufang Factor Set. In addition of Equation 5 the factor set ξ is known as Moufang factor set. The following result enables us to construct Moufang loops.

Proposition 2.1. By the previous notations, let $\Theta_1 = \{1\Theta_1, e\pi\}$ be the multiplicative group and $|\Theta_2| = \lambda > 1$, order of the group Θ_2 , with 0 isnot equal to $\sigma \in \Theta_2$. We define a mapping

$$\xi : \Theta_1 \times \Theta_1 \rightarrow \Theta_2 \text{ by}$$

$$\xi(\varrho_1, \varrho_2) = \begin{cases} \sigma, & \text{if } (\varrho_1, \varrho_2) = (e^{t\pi}, e^{t\pi}); \\ 0, & \text{if } (\varrho_1, \varrho_2) = (1_{\Theta_1}, 1_{\Theta_1}), (1_{\Theta_1}, e^{t\pi}), (e^{t\pi}, 1_{\Theta_1}). \end{cases}$$

Then $M_{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi)$ is a Moufang loop.

Example (1): Let $\Theta_1 = \{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{t\pi}\}$ be the multiplicative group and $\Theta_2 = \{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, \varpi - 1\}$ be the additive abelian group of residue classes modulo ϖ . Then Moufang loop of even order is in the form of Table 2 and Table 3.

$\otimes$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$
$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$
$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 4)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 4)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$
$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 4)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 5)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 4)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 5)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$
$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 4)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 5)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 6)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 4)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 5)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 6)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$
.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.
.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.
.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.
$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-4)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-4)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-3)$
$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$

TABLE 2. Moufang Loop of Order 2ϖ .

$\otimes$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$
$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$
$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 4)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$
$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 4)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 5)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 4)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$
$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 4)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 5)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 6)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 4)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 5)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$
.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.
.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.
.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.	.	.	.	.	...	.	.
$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-4)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-3)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-5)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-4)$
$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(e^{t\pi}, 1)$	$(e^{t\pi}, 2)$	...	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-3)$	$(e^{t\pi}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-2)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-1)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 0_{\Theta_2})$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, 1)$	...	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-4)$	$(1_{\Theta_1}, \varpi-3)$

TABLE 3. Moufang Loop of Order 2ϖ .

Example (2): If $\Theta_1 = \{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{t\pi}\}$ and $\Theta_2 = \{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 11\}$ then associated graphs of

$M_{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi)$, $\text{Nuc}^{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi)$ and $A(M_{\text{loop}}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi))$ through above mentioned edge labeling are Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 respectively

Figure 3. Complete Bipartite Graph $K_{24,24}$

Figure 4. Complete Bipartite Graph $K_{2,2}$

Figure 5. Complete Bipartite Graph $K_{2,2}$

Now we summarize all the above discussion in the following Table 4:

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Θ_1	Θ_2	Moufang loop	Nucleus	Associator subloop
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 5\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{12,12}$	$C_1, K_{1,1}$	$C_3, K_{3,3}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 7\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{16,16}$	$C_2, K_{2,2}$	$C_2, K_{2,2}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 9\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{20,20}$	$C_1, K_{1,1}$	$C_5, K_{5,5}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 11\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{24,24}$	$C_2, K_{2,2}$	$C_3, K_{3,3}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 13\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{28,28}$	$C_1, K_{1,1}$	$C_7, K_{7,7}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 15\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{32,32}$	Klein four group, $K_{4,4}$	$C_2, K_{2,2}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 17\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{36,36}$	$C_1, K_{1,1}$	$C_9, K_{9,9}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 19\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{40,40}$	$C_2, K_{2,2}$	$C_5, K_{5,5}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 21\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{44,44}$	$C_1, K_{1,1}$	$C_{11}, K_{11,11}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 23\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{48,48}$	Klein four group, $K_{4,4}$	$C_3, K_{3,3}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 25\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{52,52}$	$C_1, K_{1,1}$	$C_{13}, K_{13,13}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 27\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{56,56}$	$C_2, K_{2,2}$	$C_7, K_{7,7}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 29\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{60,60}$	$C_5, K_{5,5}$	$C_3, K_{3,3}$
$\{1_{\Theta_1}, e^{i\pi}\}$	$\{0_{\Theta_2}, 1, 2, \dots, 31\}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{loop}(\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \xi), K_{64,64}$	quaternion group, $K_{8,8}$	$C_2, K_{2,2}$

TABLE 4. Different Algebraic Structures and their Associated Graphs.

• **Discussion**

This paper deals with the interrelationship between pure mathematics and graph theory. Main purpose, in particular, is to understand those algebraic structures, non-associative Moufang loops, nucleus and associator subloops, which are closely linked with the bipartite graphs through edge labeling. One can develop more results in time to come to relate these two well known boughs of mathematics with the help of different loops constructed by p-groups and additive abelian groups.

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